

The herbaceous members of the genus *Cornus* in NW North America

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The systematic relationships of the herbaceous taxa of *Cornus* (subgen. *Arctocrania*) in NW North America have been evaluated using morphological, chemical, phytogeographical and cytological evidence. *C. canadensis* L. and *C. suecica* (both $2n=22$) are distinct species. In addition two intermediate taxa occur, viz. the semi-fertile hybrid *C. canadensis* × *suecica* ($2n=22$) and *C. unalaschkensis* ($2n=44$), believed to be an allopolyploid derivative. *C. canadensis* occurs in inland areas, while *C. unalaschkensis* has a southern coastal, and *C. suecica* a northern coastal distribution. The diploid hybrids are found in the present overlap area between *C. canadensis* and *C. suecica*. *C. unalaschkensis* is nowadays geographically isolated from the other taxa and may represent a survivor from the Pleistocene glaciations. Eight flavonoids have been found in the taxa, quercetin 3-O gentiobioside has importance as a taxonomic and phytogeographic marker.

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Relationships within the genus *Cornus* in North America have been explored in the past (Nakai 1909, Hutchinson 1942, Hara 1948, Ferguson 1966, Jensen et al. 1975) and although all these treatments are in agreement in the segregation of the herbaceous members of the genus, either as a subgenus (subgen. *Arctocrania* Endl. ex Reichenb.) or as a genus (*Chamaepericlymenum* Hill), little work has been done to elucidate the relationships of these herbaceous taxa to one another. The present study is an attempt to fill in this gap for NW North America.

The three commonly recognized species *C. canadensis* L., *C. suecica* L. and *C. unalaschkensis* Ledeb. all occur in the British Columbia, Yukon, Alaska region. *C. unalaschkensis*, because it is morphologically intermediate between the other two species, has been considered a hybrid of the two (Hultén 1937, Olsen 1914). But as pointed out by Porsild (1939), collections have been reported from over one thousand miles from the nearest *C. suecica*

location, thus casting doubt on the hybrid origin of the species.

C. canadensis is found mainly in North America, but also in NE Asia and higher altitudes in Japan (Rickett 1945, Hultén 1968). *C. suecica* is circumpolar in distribution being found disjunct on both NW and NE coasts of North America, as well as Greenland, Great Britain, Scandinavia and Siberia (Hultén 1937, 1968). *C. unalaschkensis* is found in somewhat more continental sites than *C. suecica* in NW and NE North America and Greenland (Hultén 1937, 1968).

Two chromosome numbers have been reported; a diploid number $2n=22$ and a tetraploid of $2n=44$. *C. suecica* has been reported as $2n=22$ (see Löve & Löve 1975), *C. unalaschkensis* $2n=22$ (Taylor & Brockman 1966) and $2n=44$ (Taylor & Mulligan 1968), and *C. canadensis* as $2n=22$ (Packer 1964) and $2n=44$ (Dermen 1932, Clay & Nath 1971). In the taxonomic treatment proposed by Löve & Löve

(1975) chromosome number is used as the paramount character for denoting species. Thus any tetraploid specimen is called *Chamaepericlymenum unalaschkense*. *C. canadensis* and *C. suecica* are considered strictly diploid.

The relationship of the intermediate taxon to *Cornus canadensis* and *C. suecica* is considered at present to be unclear. The morphological, phytogeographical and cytotaxonomic information so far reported is inadequate and in part contradictory.

A study of various populations of the herbaceous *Cornus* species collected throughout NW North America has been carried out using the following approaches: phytochemical data accumulated through the study of population flavonoid profiles; cytological data compiled from chromosome counts of the populations; and morphological data based on comparative population studies and hybrid indices.

Material and methods

Collections were made throughout Alberta, although primarily in the Rocky Mountain region, as well as NC British Columbia, Queen Charlotte Islands, Yukon Territory and Alaska. Living and dried material, as well as pressed specimens were obtained from most sites. Morphological variation was studied at both intraspecific and interspecific level.

Chromosome counts were made from actively growing root tips. The source of the root tips was living material transplanted from the field into 4-inch pots and grown in the greenhouse. Some root-tips were collected in the field and preserved in a solution of acetic acid and 95% ethanol (1:3). Root tips to be examined were prepared using the method of Tjio & Levan (1950). A voucher specimen for each collection is deposited at ALTA.

Guard cell length measurements were used to separate diploid and tetraploid specimens where chromosome data were unavailable. Correlation between cell size and ploidy level have previously been described by Stebbins (1971) and Sax & Sax (1937).

Preparations were made from living material by peeling the epidermis from the lower side of the leaf with a razor blade, then mounting the peel in water on a microscope slide. Length of guard cells was measured with an eyepiece micrometer at 400 \times using an A0 microscope.

Flavonoids. The flavonoids of various populations were analyzed using the methods of Mabry et al. (1969), Harborne (1975) and Ribéreau-Gayon (1972).

Whole plants used in flavonoid extraction were collected in the field and dried in paper bags. Only leaves and stems were used for extraction. Identification of the compounds was made for three separate

populations (collection nos. 75033, 75009, 75060). Approximately 20 g of dry plant material was used in the analysis. The material was eluted in c. 300 ml of 80% ethanol and ground in an Oster blender for 15 minutes. Separation of the extract was accomplished by filtration through cheesecloth and a Buchner funnel, then Whatman no. 1 or no. 2 filter paper and a Buchner funnel.

The solution was evaporated in vacuo using a Buchler rotoevaporator until reduced to approximately 50 ml. Ten drops of the extract were spotted on each of the 32 sheets of Whatman no. 3MM chromatography paper. These were run using descending chromatography in two dimensions with two different solvents. The first dimension was run using 1-butanol:acetic acid:H₂O (BAW, 4:1:5, upper phase) and the second 15% acetic acid. The resulting spots were examined using UV light (366 nm) on untreated sheets and on sheets fumed with ammonia. Spots were also examined under visible light after they had been sprayed with ferric chloride-ferrous cyanide stain or Benedict's reagent.

Spots that overlapped on the initial chromatograph could, in most cases, be separated by eluting the spots together and streaking the mixture on full-size sheets of Whatman no. 1 paper then chromatographing in one dimension, using BAW (4:1:5 BAW; upper phase) as the solvent.

Compounds exhibiting a positive reaction with both ferric chloride-ferrous cyanide (blue) and Benedict's reagent (yellow) were cut out and eluted from unstained chromatograms in a minimum amount of spectral grade methanol. They were then analyzed using UV spectrophotometer. Scans were recorded for the methanol solution, followed by scans of the solution after the addition of sodium methoxide, anhydrous aluminum trichloride, aluminum trichloride and hydrochloric acid (N), sodium acetate, and sodium acetate and boric acid (Mabry et al. 1969 pp. 35-61) (Table 1).

To further aid identification, all pure compounds were chromatographed in one-dimension using four different solvent systems on half-sheets (23 \times 57 cm) of Whatman no. 1 paper. The solvent systems were: (a) 1-butanol:acetic acid:H₂O (4:1:5, upper phase); (b) saturated phenol (80% phenol:H₂O); (c) 15% acetic acid; and (d) water.

The glycosides were then hydrolyzed to aglycone and sugar constituents by refluxing in 5-7 ml of 2N HCl. Variation in the amount of HCl added occurred because of a variation in concentration of the methanol-glycoside mixture as indicated by the colour of the solution. Refluxing was carried out for fifteen minutes in a reflux condenser at 100°C. After hydrolysis the solution was cooled and partitioned against three to five ml of diethyl ether. The lower aqueous layer containing the sugars and the upper ether layer containing the aglycones were separated. After drying the aglycone and redissolving it in spectral grade methanol, part of the extract was analyzed spectrophotometrically as outlined above and the remaining solution chromatographed in one dimension using 4:1:5 BAW. Identification in all cases was made from spectral scans and supported by Rf data. The aqueous fraction, containing the sugars, was

Table 1. Spectral and chromatographic characteristics of major flavonoids isolated in *Cornus canadensis* and its relatives. - q quenching; y yellow; ygn yellow-green; BAW n-Butanol - Acetic acid - Water (4:1:5), upper phase; Ac 15% acetic acid; Ph 80% phenol; BI band I; BII band II. - Values within parentheses: inflection. - * negative values indicate a hypsochromatic shift of band I. - All Rf's given on Whatman no. 1 paper.

Compound	Colour UV/NH ₃	Rf × 100				MeOH		NaoMe	NaoAc	AlCl ₃	HCl	+ H ₃ BO ₃
		BAW	H ₂ O	Ac ⁻	Ph	BI	BII	BI	BII	BI	BI	BI
Quercetin 3-O gentiobioside	q-y	35	17	28	40	359	258 (270)	60	11	57	*-20	16
Quercetin 3-O galactoside	q-y	68	14	37	61	361 (302)	258 (268)	65	8	60	*-30	20
Quercetin 3-O sophoroside	q-y	46	28	47	37	358 (300)	270	70	8	55	*-25	22
Quercetin 3-O glucoside	q-y	60	11	29	40	361 (298)	259 (266)	50	9	41	*-29	19
Kaempferol 3-O glucoside	q-ygn	72	18	42	70	358	268	50	8	42	0	1
Kaempferol 3-O arabinoside	q-ygn	84	28	27	34	351	268	55	8	45	*- 2	0

concentrated, then spotted on half-sheets of Whatman no. 1 paper. In each case two spots of the unknown sugars were made. To one spot was added 30 μ l of 0.005 M standard solution of glucose. The chromatographs were run using 80% isopropanol as the solvent. The sugars were stained using aniline hydrogen phthalate solution. Unknown sugars were identified by their R_g (distance from origin/distance of glucose from origin × 100) and by their colour after staining.

The remaining populations were analyzed chromatographically in two dimensions in a manner similar to that previously described, using a reduced amount of material. Three grams of dry plant material were eluted in 50 ml of 80% ethanol for each of the populations (a minimum of ten plants being used). Seven drops of extract were spotted on only two sheets of Whatman no. 3MM chromatography paper. No attempt was made to condense the extract by roto-evaporation. The two sheets were run chromatographically in two dimensions in the manner previously described and the chromatographic profiles were compared; but no attempt to elute the spots was made. A series of flavonoid profiles was obtained. Spots with the same R_f values were identified by comparison with the original major populations.

Pollen grain viability was ascertained by staining fresh pollen in a drop of lacto-phenol-cotton blue stain for five minutes. Pollen grains were considered viable if they took up stain and appeared a deep blue in colour at 200 × magnification.

Results

Analysis of the results of this study has enabled the delimitation of four taxa: two diploid species, *Cornus canadensis* (2n = 22) and *C. suecica* (2n = 22), an amphidiploid species, *C. unalaschensis* (2n = 44) and a diploid hybrid, *C.*

canadensis × *suecica* (2n = 22). In the reporting of the results the taxa will be referred to by these four names. A discussion of this classification is given later.

Morphology

Eleven key or critical characters by which *C. canadensis* and *C. suecica* specimens could be separated were chosen. They are given in Table 2.

Initial examination of the intermediate specimens collected indicated that they exhibited many combinations of the eleven character traits of the two other species. In addition, many intermediates exhibited character states between the putative parent species.

For each of the eleven characters referred to, a numerical value was given to each of the two contrasting character states; zero for the extreme associated with *C. suecica*, and one for that associated with *C. canadensis*. For states between these two extremes, a numerical value between zero and one was given (0.25; 0.5; 0.75) which reflected which extreme the character state most clearly resembled, and to what degree. The summation of the eleven numerical values for each collection gave the collection a value expressed as a percentage of the possible total of eleven. Thus *C. canadensis* will have a numerical value approaching 100% while *C. suecica* values will approach 0%. The results are given in Table 3.

Table 2. Comparative characters used in the morphological analysis. Character states for *C. canadensis* were given numerical value 1, those of *C. suecica* 0. Character states between the extremes were given an appropriate numerical value between 0 and 1.

Character	Character state <i>C. canadensis</i>	Character state <i>C. suecica</i>
Leaf length/width ratio	> 1.50	< 1.25
Leaf arrangement	whorl in 4–6 leaves at summit	3–6 subequal pairs of leaves
Leaf shape	ovate to elliptic	lanceolate to ovate
Leaf tip	acute to shortly acuminate	broadly acute to obtuse
Leaf base	narrowed at base with distinct petiole	clasping at base
Leaf venation	2–3 veins on either side of midrib	5–7 veins arising from base of leaf
Flower number	> 25	< 15
Primary branches in cyme	4 primary branches discernible	primary branches not discernible
Sepal and hypanthium colour and pubescence	cream to green; usually ciliate	blue or purplish; ciliate with blue trichomes only at base
Petal colour	yellowish	blue or purple
Stamen length	shorter than style	longer than style

Table 3. A summary of the data given for herbaceous *Cornus*.

	<i>C. canadensis</i>	<i>C. canadensis</i> × <i>suecica</i>	<i>C. unalaschkensis</i>	<i>C. suecica</i>
Chromosome number (2n)	22	22	44	22
Quercetin 3-O gentiobioside	–	–	+	+
Pollen viability	≈ 98 %	≈ 52 %	≈ 98 %	≈ 98 %
Morphological index values	92 %–100 %	64 %–79 %	31 %–89 %	21 %–28 %

Morphological analysis resulted in the recognition of a key or critical character, petal colour. *C. canadensis* lacks pigment and hence is readily distinguishable from its relatives. However, *C. suecica* at times is indistinguishable from the intermediate forms on gross morphology.

Chromosome numbers

Somatic chromosome counts were determined for 48 populations. Two chromosome numbers were present among these collections: the diploid (2n = 22) and tetraploid (2n = 44) numbers described in previous publications.

Table 4 and Fig. 1 show the distribution of these two chromosome numbers, based upon collections by the authors. For some of the locations indicated on the map, chromosome number was inferred from guard cell size because plant material necessary for obtaining a

chromosome count was unavailable. Information concerning guard cell size is contained in a later section.

Pollen viability

A test to determine pollen viability was carried out on those specimens which flowered under greenhouse conditions.

C. canadensis (2n = 22) exhibited pollen viabilities of 98 % (e.g. nos. 75005, 75008), *C. unalaschkensis* (2n = 44) showed 98 % viability (e.g. nos. 75024, 75035) and *C. canadensis* × *suecica* (2n = 22) exhibited a pollen viability of 52 % (e.g. nos. 75053 and 75054). *C. suecica* (2n = 22) gave results of 98 % (e.g. no. 75063).

Guard cells

Guard cell length was positively correlated with ploidy level. Diploid specimens possessed shorter

Fig. 1. Study sites of *Cornus*.

ter guard cells than tetraploid specimens. There was a significant difference between the mean guard cell sizes of the diploid ($\bar{x} = 25.20$; 1008 cells) and tetraploid ($\bar{x} = 32.05$; 904 cells) species as demonstrated by a two sample Student's *t*-test ($s = 1.48$, $t = 4.64$). Guard cell length of the diploids ranged from 17.9 to 38.3 μm while the guard cell length of the tetraploids ranged from 23.0 to 43.4 μm (Fig. 2). No evidence of a difference in guard cell size between different species of the same chromosome number was found.

Floral development and reproduction

No experiments were carried out to ascertain the type of breeding system found in the herbaceous *Cornus* species. However, some observations were made of the floral development of plants in the greenhouse.

At the tip of each flower bud, attached to one of the four petals is an awn-like projection which stands erect from the bud. The bud itself is similar to a small tent in structure, with the stamens bent and completely enclosed by the

Fig. 2. Guard cell length in *Cornus*. ● diploids (1008 cells), ○ tetraploids (904 cells).

four petals. The whole bud springs open when the awn-like projection is touched. Simultaneously, the anthers dehisce, sending a cloud of pollen into the air. Much of the pollen lands on the flower's own stigma. Fruit very seldom developed in the greenhouse. Self-incompatibility is suspected as the means to prevent obligate selfing. The most likely means of triggering the bud opening and pollen release is the touching of the awn-like projection by an insect. The insect could act as a pollen carrier, effecting cross-pollination.

Vegetative reproduction by means of rhizomes is very commonly observed in the field.

Flavonoids

The results reported are based upon separate extracts, prepared from dried plant material from the collections by the authors (Table 4).

Glycosides of both kaempferol and quercetin were isolated from all collections examined (Table 1). The kaempferol glycosides were visible on the chromatogram as one spot but further chromatography separated the spot into two entities with a possible third compound visible. After identification of the two easily discernible spots as kaempferol 3-O glucoside and kaemp-

Table 4. Site locations used in present study. * Chromosome number determination based on guard cell measurements. – Ala Alaska, Alb Alberta, BC British Columbia.

Coll. no. Locality

Cornus canadensis – 2n = 22

75003	Alb	Pigeon Lake, 53°10' N, 114°W
75004	Alb	Rocky Mountain House, 52°20' N, 114°40' W
75005	Alb	Rocky Mountain House, 52°30' N, 115°30' W
75006	Alb	Herbert Lake, 51°28' N, 116°13' W
75007	Alb	Lake Louise, 51°30' N, 116°15' W
75008	Alb	Mount Norquay, 51°15' N, 115°35' W
76101	Alb	Cypress Hills, Reesor Lake
76102	Alb	Cypress Hills, Spruce Coulee
75009	BC	Golden, 51°15' N, 116°40' W
75011	BC	Radium, 50°40' N, 115°50' W
75012*	BC	Altitude Creek
75013	BC	Sunshine Village
75014	BC	Lake Minnewanka, 51°15' N, 115°30' W
75036	BC	Smithers, 54°30' N, 127°50' W
75040	BC	McBride, 55 mile W of Hwy. 16
75041	BC	Jasper, 75 miles W
75073*	BC	Summit Lake
75043	Ala	N. Paxon, 64°01' N, 145°20' W
75044	Ala	Denali, Mile 10
75047	Ala	Denali, Mile 25
75050	Ala	McLaren River, Denali
75056	Ala	Fairbanks, 64°30' N, 147°10' W
75058*	Ala	Eagle, 64°10' N, 141°15' W
75059	Ala	Palmer, 61°55' N, 147°20' W

Cornus unalaschkensis – 2n = 44

75017	BC	Moresby Lake (Queen Charlotte Islands)
75019	BC	Moresby Lake, 52°55' N, 130°05' W
75024	BC	West Victoria Lake (Q.C.I.)
75026	BC	Upper Victoria Lake (Q.C.I.)
75029*	BC	Graham Island
75030	BC	West Tow, 54°02' N, 129°50' W
75031*	BC	Tow Hill, 54°05' N, 129°50' W
75032	BC	Tlell River, 53°30' N, 129°55' W
75033	BC	Olive Lake, 54°20' N, 130°15' W
75035	BC	New Hazelton, 55°20' N, 127°40' W
75036*	BC	Smithers, 54°30' N, 127°50' W
75038	BC	Purden Lake, 53°55' N, 121°55' W
76105	Ala	Petersburg, 56°55' N, 133°W
76110*	Ala	Chilkat Lake, Haines
76111*	Ala	Haines

Cornus suecica – 2n = 22

75060	Ala	N. Anchorage, 61°30' N, 149°20' W
75063	Ala	Seward, 60°45' N, 148°35' W

Cornus canadensis × **suecica** – 2n = 22

75046	Ala	Paxon, 63°10' N, 145°20' W
75048	Ala	McLaren River, Denali
75053	Ala	McKinley Park, 60°30' N, 150°20' W
75054	Ala	Seward, 60°10' N, 149°30' W
75065	Ala	Mile 12, N. Houston
75066	Ala	Mile 102, Hwy. 3

ferol 3-O arabinoside, the original large spot was hydrolyzed. The only aglycone present in the large spot was kaempferol; however, three sugars, glucose, arabinose and galactose were isolated. By inference, this third compound was identified as kaempferol 3-O galactoside. No Rf data and spectral data is present for this compound due to its low concentration.

Seven of the eight flavonols identified were present in all the collections examined, while the eighth, here named quercetin 3-O gentiobioside, was found only in *C. suecica* and *C. unalaschkensis*.

Distribution and habitats

Collections of *Cornus unalaschkensis* were made mainly along the NW coast of North America. In addition, collections from continental B. C. were made – Purden Lake (75038) and New Hazelton (75035) (Fig. 1). All collections were made from a coastal forest habitat dominated by *Picea sitchensis* (Bong.) Carv. and *Tsuga heterophylla* (Raf.) Sarg., far from the peat bogs which intersperse the coastal forest, where *Pinus contorta* Dougl. is the dominant tree species.

Cornus suecica is also restricted to a primarily coastal environment, and no significant difference between this species and *C. unalaschkensis* was found. *C. suecica* is much more northern than *C. unalaschkensis*. *C. suecica* has been reported from SE Alaska and N British Columbia (Hultén 1937, Taylor & McBryde 1977) but populations resembling *C. suecica* collected by us in these areas were all *C. unalaschkensis*. However, we have not studied all herbarium material available, so partial sympatry would still appear to be a possibility.

Cornus canadensis is more continental in our area and is thus found in an area with less rainfall than the coastal forest, in association with, e.g. *Populus tremuloides* Michx., *Picea glauca* (Moench) Voss or *Pinus contorta*.

The diploid hybrid is restricted to the present-day overlap areas of the parent species. It grows in habitats of a more continental type similar to *Cornus canadensis* at its northern limits in central Alaska.

Discussion

Flavonoid profile

The flavonoid profile of the *C. canadensis*-*C. suecica* complex is relatively simple. The presence of only flavonol glycosides in the complex indicates a modest chemical diversity (Harborne & Williams 1971, Rossler et al. 1966). The step from woody to herbaceous habit in plants has been shown to produce three typical changes in leaf flavonoids (Swain 1975): loss of proanthocyanidins, loss of b-ring trihydroxylation, and replacement of flavonols by flavones. Because members of the *C. canadensis*-*C. suecica* complex are the only herbaceous members of an otherwise woody genus, it is therefore not surprising that they only exhibit one of these chemical changes, viz. loss of b-hydroxylation (lack of myricetin). There is no evidence of flavones replacing flavonols.

Inheritance of quercetin 3-O gentiobioside

Cornus suecica (diploid) and *C. unalaschkensis* (tetraploid) invariably have quercetin 3-O gentiobioside, while *C. canadensis* and *C. canadensis* × *suecica* (both diploids) lack this compound. If one assumes that *C. unalaschkensis* is the autotetraploid derivative of *C. suecica*, then this chemical pattern is easy to explain. However, the morphology of the tetraploids speaks against this. The presence of a diploid hybrid, morphologically intermediate between *C. suecica* and *C. canadensis*, and therefore extremely similar to *C. unalaschkensis*, strongly indicates that the latter originated by chromosome doubling in such a hybrid.

Since the diploid hybrid lacks quercetin 3-O gentiobioside, it is likely that the production of this compound is controlled by a recessive gene. In the tetraploid derivative of the diploid heterozygous hybrid, the gene will again be present in double dosage, which will lead to production of gentiobioside.

Previous classification

Previous attempts to classify these taxa have relied heavily upon morphology, which has resulted in confusion. For example, petal colour was considered by Calder & Taylor (1965) to be the diagnostic character by which *C.*

canadensis, *C. suecica* and *C. unalaschkensis* could be separated. The petals of *C. suecica* were thought to be completely purple, those of the intermediate to be only partially purple. This was not found to be so in this study.

Another classification based strictly upon morphological characters was proposed by Lepage (1946, 1950, 1955) who described a wide range of forms, separated mainly on leaf and bract abnormalities. The results of the present study indicate that these forms are rare and are most often contained in populations of otherwise normal *C. canadensis*. These forms are, therefore, not accepted as separate taxa.

Taxonomy

The complex is most accurately treated as consisting of three morphological groups: *C. canadensis* (diploid), *C. suecica* (diploid) and an intermediate group, which can be subdivided into *C. unalaschkensis* (tetraploid) and *C. canadensis* × *suecica* (diploid). The use of all eleven morphological characters does, in most cases, give an accurate classification. *C. canadensis* is easily identified by its green flowers; all other plants have at least some purple tinge of the petals. Other identifications based on morphology are not completely reliable, so cytological and flavonoid evidence must be used.

Cornus canadensis and *C. suecica* can be separated from one another quite easily. They differ in morphology, chemistry, distribution and ecology, and their diploid hybrid is semisterile. For these reasons no change in their taxonomic status is proposed.

However, 50% of the pollen in those specimens of the hybrid examined was viable and this leaves the possibility for introgression. No evidence of such a process has been found in the material and diploid hybrids growing beside *C. canadensis* (no. 75052, 75048, 75046) showed no evidence of interbreeding. The sterility of the hybrid has been observed in the field by Hultén (1937) and Olsen (1914).

The intermediates are, as evident from the facts presented here, the results of hybridization; the tetraploid has been derived through chromosome doubling from an initial diploid intermediate, probably closely similar to the present-day one. The wide range of the tetra-

ploid and its occurrence outside the areas of the putative parents, together with its fertility, indicates that the tetraploid represents an older cycle of hybridization than the diploid hybrids.

The allotetraploid intermediate, because it is fully fertile and reproductively isolated, is considered to be a distinct species, *Cornus unalaschkensis* Ledeb. Ledebour (1842) described this species with no knowledge of floral characters and the description of the leaf venation pattern does not fit the type specimen. We have seen the type specimen, and it clearly represents an intermediate. Examination of the guard cells of a collection from the type location (CAN 326919) suggests that it is a tetraploid.

Although morphology does not allow the easy distinction of *Cornus unalaschkensis* from the diploid hybrid, they can be separated on chromosome number, guard cell size, pollen viability, distribution and presence of quercetin 3-O gentiobioside. The formula *Cornus canadensis* × *suecica* has been chosen to delimit the diploid hybrid.

Evolution and ranges

Hybridization has occurred between the two diploid species, *Cornus canadensis* and *C. suecica*. In the earliest of the two known instances a chromosome doubling produced a fully fertile allotetraploid. This tetraploid survived the Pleistocene glaciations and climatic changes in areas where *C. suecica* failed to survive, so the present southern extremities of the distribution of the tetraploid and that of *C. suecica* are widely separate. The second instance of hybridization has occurred in more recent times result-

ing in formation of a diploid entity in the present overlap areas of the two species. The eventual production of the tetraploid in these overlap areas is certainly possible and would represent an example of polytopic speciation. The difference in geographic distribution between diploids and tetraploids is perhaps the result of reinvasion after glaciation. Hultén (1968) suggested that *C. suecica* once had a more southerly distribution which has been reduced due to a change in climate, whereas the tetraploid has apparently not suffered the same reduction in distribution. These climatic changes may also have changed the distribution of *C. suecica* enough to create a new "overlap area" with *C. canadensis*, and allow the process of hybridization to begin again in a new, more northern area.

The coastal areas, now occupied by the tetraploid, were all glaciated during the last advance of the ice, although various coastal refugia or unglaciated areas may have existed along the coast (Heusser 1965, Savile 1968, Randhawa & Beamish 1972). As the ice receded the areas were reinvaded by the tetraploid. The more northern areas, although also unglaciated in many parts, do not show evidence of invasion by the tetraploid, perhaps because the tetraploid race may not have existed so far north in pre-glacial times and so was not present to invade these areas.

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Key to *Cornus* subgen. *Arctocrania* in NW North America

1. Flowers greenish-white; stamens mostly shorter than the style; hypanthium hoary *C. canadensis*
- Flowers purple or partly purple; stamens mostly longer than the style; hypanthium sparsely strigillose to hoary 2
2. Leaves mostly arranged in a whorl of 4-6 at the shoot apex, often with 1-2 pairs of stem leaves 4-6 cm below the whorl; leaves mostly petiolate, sometimes sessile; leaf veins arising from a distinct midrib, seldom from the leaf base 3
- Leaves mostly arranged in 3-6 subequal pairs, sometimes simulating a whorl at the shoot apex; leaves sessile to sub-sessile; leaf veins arising from the base or if from the midrib, from the basal 1/4 to 1/3 of the leaf *C. suecica*
3. Distribution restricted to continental Alaska; chromosome number $2n=22$; pollen approximately 50% inviable; quercetin 3-O gentiobioside absent *C. canadensis* × *suecica*
- Distribution restricted to coastal northwestern North America (including the Aleutian Is.) and the western side of the Rocky Mountains; chromosome number $2n=44$; pollen mostly all viable; quercetin 3-O gentiobioside present *C. unalaschkensis*

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